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A Case Study of the Drip and Sprinkler Water Irrigation System in India

Jadav Santoshkumar Chhaganbhai*

ABSTRACT

Water is becoming increasingly scarce worldwide and more than one-third of the world population would face absolute water scarcity by the year 2025. The worst affected areas would be semi-arid regions of Asia, the Middle-East and sub-Saharan Africa, all of which are already having a heavy concentration of population living below poverty line. The situation in India is also critical, where absolute water scarcity is already affecting a substantial part of the population and this proportion is increasing rapidly. Much of the water scarcity in India is due to spatial variation in demand and supply of water.

INTRODUCTION

Irrigation is the largest water consuming sector, accounting for more than 80 % of the total withdrawals. Yet, irrigation so far has covered only about 40 % of the gross cropped area, even though India has the largest irrigated area in the world. Given the increasing scarcity and also non-agricultural water demand, demand management is receiving special attention. In India, although a number of demand management strategies in the irrigation sector have been introduced with a view to increasing the water use efficiency, however the net impact of these strategies in increasing the water use efficiency so far has not been very impressive. One of the demand management strategies introduced relatively recently to manage water consumption in Indian agriculture is micro-irrigation. Unlike flood method of irrigation, micro-irrigation supplies water at the required interval and in desired quantity at the location where water is demanded using a pipe network, emitters and nozzles. Therefore, MI in principle should result in low conveyance and distribution losses and lead to higher water use efficiency. Among advanced micro-irrigation techniques, drip and sprinklers are gaining special attention. Drip irrigation and sprinkler irrigation methods have distinct characteristics in parameters such as flow rate, pressure requirement, wetted area and mobility, but they have the potential of

significantly increasing water use efficiency. While DIM supplies water directly to the root zone through a network of pipes and emitters, SIM sprinkles water, similar to rainfall, into the air through nozzles which subsequently breaks into small water drops and fall on the field surface.

DIM is highly suitable for wide spaced crops, but it is also being used for cultivating oilseeds, pulses, cotton and even for wheat crop. SIM is mostly suitable for closely grown crops like cereals, pulses, wheat, sugarcane, groundnut, cotton, vegetables, fruits, flowers, spices and condiments. An experimental study suggests that sprinklers can also be used successfully for cultivating paddy crop. Unlike conventional method, MI also has the advantage of irrigating undulating terrain, rolling topography, hilly areas, barren land and areas which have shallow soils. In spite of many advantages, MI coverage in India, except in a few states, is not appreciable. High capital investments, little or no cost of surface irrigation supplies; free electricity for pumping groundwater have been the important impediments for faster adoption of MI techniques.

However, an increase in the DIM adoption has taken place since the 1980s, mainly as a result of various promotional programmes introduced by the Central and State Governments. In spite of the enormous potential for different crops, not many studies seem to have been undertaken to analyse the potential and prospects of drip and sprinkler irrigation for different states in India. This paper, using the available secondary information, attempts to fill this void.

IMPORTANCE OF THE DRIP AND SPRINKLER WATER IRRIGATION

Apart from the saving of water, this would also help achieve cultivation of sugarcane in a sustainable manner. Despite irrigation water shortage in many states, not only does the area under sugarcane continue to grow at a relatively faster rate, but it is cultivated predominantly under flood method of irrigation. This puts additional pressure on our limited water resources. Drip set manufacturers should be asked to involve intensively in promoting micro-irrigation by organizing frequent demonstrations at farmers' fields. Since the use of micro-irrigation is still in the take-off stage in India, an active role of the manufacturers is essential in promoting drip irrigation as well as developing confidence among the farmers about the usefulness of this new technology. The micro-system manufacturers should be involved in providing

advice on agronomic packages to the farmers so as to encourage the adoption of WSTs on a large scale.

For a speedy growth of micro-irrigation, a special package scheme can be introduced where priority can be given to providing bank loans for digging wells and electricity connection for those farmers who are ready to adopt micro-irrigation for cultivating any crop. Groundwater is the only source of water being used for drip method of irrigation in India. Unlike other countries, water from surface sources is not used for drip method of irrigation. Since water use efficiency under surface sources is very low owing to heavy losses through conveyance and distribution, farmers should be encouraged to use water from surface sources for drip method of irrigation. This can be done by allocating a certain proportion of water from each irrigation projects only for the use of micro-irrigation.

One of the important reasons for the low spread of this technology even in the water-scarce area is the availability of highly subsidized canal water as well as electricity for irrigation pump sets. Appropriate pricing policies on these two inputs may also encourage the farmers to adopt this technology.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the past trends in drip and sprinkler irrigated area across states.
2. To estimate the potential area for drip and sprinkler irrigation in different states.
3. To suggest policies for increasing the adoption of WST sin the future.

TRENDS IN AREA UNDER DRIP AND SPRINKLER IRRIGATION

DIM and SIM adoption in India are not the same across crops and regions. While DIM is largely found in states like Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu, SIM is largely adopted in states like Haryana, Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh.

DRIP AND SPRINKLER WATER SYSTEM IRRIGATION BENEFITS, POTENTIAL AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Crops that are cultivated with these two methods of irrigation are also not the same. As already mentioned, wide spaced crops are highly suited for DIM, whereas

close spaced crops are suitable for SIM. Therefore, we assess the DIM and SIM trends separately. The development of DIM was very slow initially, but its spread increased significantly since 1990s due to various promotional schemes introduced by the Government of India and states like Maharashtra. DIM area increased from a mere 1,500 ha in 1985 to 70,589 ha in 1991-92, and to 2,46,000 ha in 1997-98. As of 2003, the DIM area has increased to about 450 thousand hectares, of which 78 % of the area is under Government of India Schemes.

However, as mentioned in the Report of the Task Force on Micro-irrigation, a large number of institutions, commercial organisations, universities, large public/private sector companies, NGOs, etc., have taken up drip irrigation in the country for their farms/crops, which are estimated to be of about 1,00,000 ha in area. This area has not been reflected in the estimate made by the government departments. Therefore, the total DIM area in the country could be as high as 500,000 hectares as of March 2003 (GOI 2004).

DRIP IRRIGATED AREA HAS INCREASED SUBSTANTIALLY

During all the three time periods studied, Maharashtra State alone accounted for nearly 50 % of India's total drip irrigated area, followed by Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh. However, DIM area still constitutes a very small proportion of the total irrigated area in all the states in India - only 0.48 % of the gross irrigated area and about 1.09 % of the gross groundwater irrigated area in 2000-01. Although DIM technology can be applied to over 80 crops in India, its use so far has been limited to only a few crops. As of 1997-98, coconut, grapes, banana, citrus, mango and pomegranate together accounted for 67 % of the total DIM area. Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Karnataka account for a major share of the area of the above crops. For example, Maharashtra alone accounted for 93 % of the 26,460 ha of the banana area under drip irrigation. It clearly suggests that despite having severe water scarcity in different regions, the adoption of the drip method of irrigation is only concentrated in a few states. Sprinkler irrigation method is relatively old for Indian farmers as compared with drip irrigation method. Sprinkler was introduced in India during the mid-1950s for plantation crops like coffee and tea. Over the years, SIM spread into large areas in states like Haryana, Rajasthan, MP, Maharashtra and Karnataka. Unlike DIM, detailed and accurate statistics are lacking for sprinkler irrigation.

The reasons for the large-scale adoption of sprinkler irrigation vary from state to state. Though MP receives medium rainfall, it is irregular and the summer has long dry spells. This encourages MP farmers to adopt sprinkler irrigation for crops like soybean in various parts of the state. In Haryana, the soil condition, topography and the climates that are prevailing in the south western part of the state, especially in districts of Bhiwani, Mahendergarh, Rothak, Sirsa and Hisar, have prompted the adoption of sprinkler irrigation. Similarly, favourable cropping patterns for MI and water scarcity during the summer season are the main reasons for the relatively higher adoption of sprinkler irrigation in Rajasthan. Although the SIM reported area is much higher than that under drip irrigation, no reliable data is available on the composition of crops that are cultivated presently using this method of irrigation. The INCID 1998 report presents a whole lot of information about the sprinkler method, but does not provide where and what crops are cultivated under this method. In fact, reliable and time series data on micro-irrigation is seldom available even for research purpose. Agencies involved in promoting MI should make all efforts to publish data on the development of micro-irrigation in terms of crop composition, area by state, districts and different size classes, area by state promoted schemes and other schemes. This would help one to analyse the underlying factors and suggest possible ways and means to increase the adoption of such water saving technologies.

POTENTIAL AREAS FOR DRIP AND SPRINKLER IRRIGATION IN INDIA

In spite of the large capital investments, MI seems to generate better returns for farmers, even without government subsidies. Although micro-irrigation has proved to be a very useful method for efficient use of irrigation water, not many studies have attempted to estimate the total potential area for drip and sprinkler method of irrigation for different states in India. Therefore, in this section, we try to estimate the total potential area for drip and sprinkler irrigation methods across different states in India. It appears that there are some methodological problems with the available estimates.

1. It is not clear whether the estimates include irrigated cropped area alone or both irrigated plus un-irrigated cropped area.
2. It also appears that the TFMI estimate includes both irrigated and un-irrigated cropped areas. Since water sources are needed to use micro-irrigation,

one should not include un-irrigated cropped area while estimating potential area for drip and sprinkler irrigation.

3. Moreover; both the estimates have not provided state-wise potential, which reflect the true variation of land use and cropping pattern.
4. We make a fresh attempt to estimate the potential area for drip and sprinkler irrigation separately covering all the major states.
5. Various crops that are highly suitable for drip method of irrigation are extensively cultivated in different parts of India.
6. Micro-irrigation is not only suitable for those areas that are presently under cultivation, but it can also be operated efficiently in undulating terrain, rolling topography, hilly areas, barren lands and areas which have shallow soils.
7. Lands (area) that are falling under the categories of barren and uncultivable lands, cultural wastelands and fallow lands can be treated as 'distant potential'.
8. In India, as per the land utilization data of 2000-01, about 56.28 million hectares of land is available under these categories. Unlike FIM, land-levelling and ploughing are not necessary for cultivating crops under DIM. Therefore, without incurring heavy expenditures on land reclamation activities, these areas could be brought under DIM cultivation in a phased manner. As expected the potential area available from each state varies considerably, because of varied cropping pattern and availability of irrigation facilities. Among the states, Uttar Pradesh has more potential followed by Rajasthan, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Punjab and Madhya Pradesh. In fact, Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan and Punjab together account for about 50 % of India's total potential area for drip method of irrigation.

THE CHARACTERISTICS OF SPRINKLER IRRIGATION METHODS

While drip method of irrigation is highly suitable for wide spaced crops, sprinkler irrigation is mostly suitable for closely grown crops like cereals and millets, and also for horticultural crops. Experimental studies do suggest that SIM is suitable for even paddy crops. SIM also suits undulating terrain, rolling topography, hilly areas, barren lands and areas which have shallow soils. But these areas are not under irrigation, so we exclude them too. The total potential can go up to 74.2mha, if paddy area is also included for estimation. Similar to drip potential area, the potential area available for SIM also varies across the states, because of the differences in

cropping pattern and irrigation availability. Our estimates show that UP state alone accounts for about 27.70 % of India's total potential, followed by Rajasthan, Punjab, Haryana, MP and Bihar.

We presume that the large-scale adoption of sprinkler irrigation may not take place immediately given the low canal water rates and electricity tariffs. Therefore, it is prudent to classify the potential into two as 'soft' and 'hard' potential so that policy decision can be made easily for achieving the target. It is to be noted here that the potential area for drip and sprinkler method of irrigation is expected to change over time depending upon the land use pattern, crop pattern, irrigated area and the level of groundwater exploitation across states.

SOME SPECIFIC INTERVENTIONS NEEDED ARE PRESENTED

1. Sprinkler irrigation has generally been promoted through subsidy schemes and not as an on-farm water and land management strategy.
2. In certain states, under subsidy scheme, no consideration is given in respect of field size, shape, topography, type and the location of water source, seasonal fluctuations, type of soil and crops to be grown.
3. Both drip and sprinkler irrigation is driven through the state and central government sponsored subsidy schemes.
4. In order to earn quick profit from the subsidy programs, many companies are marketing various sub-standard components in the market.
5. There has been a significant development in sprinkler technology all over the world. Several variations of sprinkler irrigation system, with improved design and components are available in those countries, where it is popularly used.
6. One of the major reasons for the slow growth of micro-irrigation in India is the high initial investment. In spite of the availability of subsidy from state agencies, the majority of the farmers are reluctant to invest in micro-irrigation system even in horticulture crops, which is highly suitable for drip irrigation.
7. It is understood from the field studies that capital cost required to install drip irrigations relatively high. Because of this reason, considerable percentage of farmers have expressed that they are unable to adopt this technology for low- value crops.
8. If drip system is made available at a low cost, area under drip irrigation can be increased at faster rate.

9. The centrally sponsored scheme of drip irrigation does not provide a subsidy for the sugarcane crop. The logic behind this is not clearly known. Since it is an important and also a heavy water-consuming crop, this restriction should be removed to increase the drip irrigated area at a faster rate.
10. The rate of subsidy provided through government schemes is fixed uniformly for both water-intensive as well as less water-intensive crops.
11. Differential subsidy rates can be fixed based on the types of crops and the rate of consumption of water. Uniform level of subsidy schemes currently followed for water-scarce and water-abundant areas need to be changed and higher subsidy should be provided for those regions where the scarcity of water is acute and exploitation of groundwater is very high as well.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY INTERVENTIONS

The estimate presented in the preceding section suggests that the potential for both drip and sprinkler irrigation is very large in different states of India. Micro-irrigation reduces the cost of cultivation, weed problems, soil erosion and increases water use efficiency as well as electricity use efficiency, besides helping reduce the overexploitation of groundwater. Additionally most of this development has been due to the support from state agency. Quite a few policy and technical reasons have been identified for the slow growth and the adoption of WSTs in India. Given the vast potential benefits of micro-irrigation and fast decline of irrigation water potential in the country, a number of technical and policy interventions are required to be introduced so as to increase the adoption of micro-irrigation in India.

CONCLUSION

The potential area for MI presented above is estimated based on the present cropping pattern and irrigation coverage of different states in India. One may not be able to argue that this potential area would be the same even after 10 or 20 years because of changes in the parameters that determine MI potential. The potential area available for MI is governed by factors such as cropping pattern, irrigation coverage, groundwater scarcity, price of canal water, price of electricity as well as its supply for agriculture, technology development in MI, proactive policy of the state and central governments. In case farmers shift the cropping pattern more in favour of horticultural crops because of their high profitability, the potential area for DIM

might increase significantly in the future. Similarly, if the depletion in groundwater in different regions aggravates further, it might also encourage the farmers to shift the irrigation method from flood to MI methods. One may be able to find some interesting results if comprehensive analysis is carried out covering the issues flagged here.

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